

Assessing Public Awareness on Strategic Impact of Environmental Education, Laws and Policies on Environmental Sustainability in Coastal Areas of Ondo State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Environmental problems and its allied issues are national topics of discourse in Nigeria particularly, among the environmentalists, owing to the contribution of environmental resources to economic, growth, development of Nigeria and healthy living of Nigerians; thus, necessitated this study. Descriptive survey research design was used. The population of the study comprised, people in coastal areas Ondo State, Nigeria (Ilaje and Ese-Odo Local Governments Areas) in Ondo State, Nigeria. The sample size of the study was Four hundred (400) respondents, selected through, a snow-balling sampling technique. Three research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study. A mixed research instruments (quantitative and qualitative) to generate data were used. Quantitative data were collected through a self-developed research instrument by the researcher, titled "Questionnaire on Assessing Public Awareness on Strategic Impact of Environmental Education, Laws and Policies on Environmental Sustainability in Coastal Areas of Ondo State, Nigeria". It was fashioned on four- liker rating scale; strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD), rated on 4:3:2 and points 1, respectively. Qualitative research instrument (Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) was used to collect qualitative data. The research instruments were validated by two experts in Test and Measurement, while its reliability were determined through, test-retest method at two weeks interval, and 0.71 coefficient reliability was obtained Data on Demographic characteristics of the respondents were analyzed, using Bar chart for age and gender variables while, Pie-chart was used to analyze variables like; marital and level of education, respectively. Data generated on the research questions were analyzed, using descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency counts and mean, while, qualitative data obtained were collated, analyzed and transcribed qualitatively. Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were made that public was not aware of Environmental education laws and policies on environmental issues and also, its strategic impact to halt human beings' destructive and hazardous behaviours on the environment. Based on the conclusions, recommendations were made that more pro-active strategies on Environmental education should be adopted to ensure that public is well sensitized on environmental challenges. Also, the people's whose their actions and in-actions are dangerous to the environment should be made to face the wrath of laws in order to create public attention on the existing environmental laws and policies, and hosts.

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Background to the Study

Nigeria's economy largely depends on revenues which are accruing and generating from environmental resources. Agagu (2007), stated that Nigeria is highly blessed with abundant natural resources, such as; crude oil, rivers, rocks, rich soil, bitumen, forests, kaolin and others. However, the reality today is that there is a high level of environmental destruction, degradation and mismanagement, thus, resulted into poor economy of the nation, poor condition of living of Nigerians and further, accentuating high level of crimes and criminality in the country.

The concept, environment is polemic and subject of pluralism in terms of its definition and explanation. The environment encompasses both the living and non-living things (Onuoha, Nnaemaka and Ochequwu, (2022). Environment consists of (biotic plants, animals and microbes), and abiotic (edaphic, climatic, pyric and topographic relief) components. The physical and biotic settings in which people, animals and plants live and work is referred to as the environment. Today, in the world, efforts are being made to protect the environment, Nigeria, inclusive. In Nigeria, government efforts at all levels are geared towards protecting the environment. There is no doubt that environment is under a great strain than ever before, and that humans' needs largely depend on healthy environment.

Olaniyan, Erinsakin, Akinyombo and Obe, (2020), attributed environmental destruction to human actions and in-actions. The demand for food, water and land, as well as our increasing demand for energy are destroying aqua-habitat, contaminating the air and water, and driving animals and plants species to an extinction. Presently, as reported by Bio Explorer (2021), "bio-diversity is being lost at a rate that is up to ten thousand quicker than it was hundred years, ago. In Nigeria, there are evidences of environmental degradation, destruction and mismanagement particularly, in the coastal areas or Niger-Delta areas where, there are oil mining and crude oil exploration activities of multinational companies, such as; Mobil, Shell, Chevron, Oando, Addalax, Nexen, Exxon-Mobil, and so on. Crude oil exploration in Niger-Delta region coupled, with other forms of environmental mismanagement have resulted into untold hardship and poor condition of living of a higher number of Nigerian populace. Further, aqua-habitats have been made unsafe for living while, water resources and the environment are no longer friendly with living organisms

“Nigeria water is contaminated by a variety of pollutants, both points and non-point sources, most industries dump their waste products directly into surface water sources, such as lakes and streams, without proper treatment (Oluoha et al, 2022).”

The picture depicted and painted above on environmental mismanagement and degradation is a perfect reflection of environmental challenges, particularly in the coastal areas of the country. The realization of negative effects of environmental degradation and mismanagement therefore, informed several strategies, such as; Environmental education, laws and policies to halt or reduce the unsavory trend and occurrence in the country by the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN). Environmental Education is a process of creating an environmentally literate populace, development of knowledge, enhancing people 'skills towards sustaining the environment Environmental Education focuses on gaining awareness to find solutions to issues and problems of the environment .

The industrial growth and revolutions have led to over exploitation and excessive damage of the environmental substances. Therefore, there is a need to strike a balance between environment and technological development, so that, sustainable development can be guaranteed . This also resulted into the United Nations Conference tagged the Stockholm Declaration on the Human Environment, 1972 which for the first time in the history of the world, presented a communique on a legal regime for environmental protection and also, highlighted the problems and recommended measures to be adopted in other to make the system of regulatory environmental management more effective. Nigeria was not an exception to the slow development of Environmental laws. Hitherto, Nigeria had no single policy or law relating to environmental protection. This has caused a lot of hazards and impunity on the environment .The desire and commitment of Federal Government of Nigeria, therefore, necessitated the enactment of Environmental laws Act of 1988. The promulgation of first Environmental laws in Nigeria was due to the incidence of KOKO Toxic waste that, was dumped at KOKO in Delta State, the then (Bendel State) in 1988. This incidence was considered as detrimental and injurious to the environment and human beings.

Environmental law is a complex and inter-locking body of treaties, conventions statute, regulations, and common law that operate to regulate the interaction of human beings and the rest of bio-physical and natural environments .Also, to reduce disastrous human activities on the

natural environment. In the words of a former member of International Court of Justice (ICJ). Honorable, Prince Bola Ajibola

“It is the policy of the administration to vigorously pursue the protection of the Nigerian environment in order to preserve and improve the quality of life of all citizens and conserve the resources for the benefits of future generations of Nigerians”.

Besides, Environmental laws, there are some policies that were adopted to protect the environment. Okorodudu- Fubara (1998), stated the following as some of the national environmental policies on the Environment in Nigeria;

1. The Federal Environmental Protection: Agency Decree 1988, NO 58. It was the first of its kind, since Nigeria Independence in 1960 which is in line with 1972 Stockholm Conference on environment which, Nigeria was a signatory to.
2. The Harmful Waste Special Criminal Provision Decree 1988, No 42. This policy moved Nigeria away as a mere control and compensation of hazards rather, included laws meant for monitoring, reduction, and possible prevention of environmental pollution ,and hosts.

Despite the adoption of Environmental education, laws and policies , environmental challenges are yet to be abated thus, raised some pertinent questions, such as; are people not aware of the extant Environmental Laws and policies in the country? Are people ignorant of their actions and in-actions which are hazardous on environmental resources? The researcher also observed that most of the extant researches on environment and allied issues had been self-reported without empirical validation on assessment on public awareness on strategic impact of Environmental education, laws and policies on environmental sustainability. These identified gaps therefore, spurred and motivated the researcher to carry out the study.

Statement of the Study

Environmental degradation and mismanagement have negative impact on the environment both, (living and non-living). Human actions and in-actions have been attributed as causes of environmental challenges in Nigeria, thus, necessitated Environmental education, laws and policies with the intention of creating public awareness and also to deter people’s destructive activities on the environment. Despite the plethora of integrated and strategic approaches to conserve the environment, destruction of ozone- layer, bio-sphere, air and water pollution, dumping of toxic waste inside rivers, oceans, bush burning, land over-grazing are still common

occurrences and practices in the country, Nigeria, specifically, in Ondo State. Ondo State is highly blessed with abundant natural resources, particularly at the coastal or riverine part of the state. This qualifies the state to be categorized as a member of oil producing states in the country.

Observably, there is still a high rate of environmental degradation in the riverine areas comprised, mainly Ilaje and Eze- Odo Local Government Areas of the state. This study was therefore conducted on assessing public awareness on strategic impact of Environmental education, laws and policies on environmental sustainability in coastal areas of Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

Three research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study.

1. Are you aware of Environmental education laws and policies on environmental issues?
2. Are you aware that environment can be protected through the knowledge of Environmental Education in the coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria?
3. Do you think Environmental laws and policies can adequately halt all forms of human beings people's destructive and hazardous behaviours towards the environment in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was on assessing public awareness on strategic impact of Environmental Education, laws and policies on environmental sustainability in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria, while the specific objectives were to:

1. determine whether or not peoples are aware that the environment can be protected through the knowledge of Environmental Education in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria;
2. ascertain, public perception on Environmental law, as the best strategy to sustain the environment in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria; and
3. establish whether or not public are of the knowledge that environmental resources can be conserved in coastal areas of Ondo State, Ondo, Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

Environmental Education

Environmental education has been variously explained and defined. Environmental education can be defined as a process directed at creating awareness and understanding about environmental issues that leads to responsible individuals and group actions .

Environmental Education is a learning process that increases people's knowledge and awareness about the environment and associated challenges, develops the necessary skills and expertise to address the challenges and fosters attitudes, motivations, and commitments to make informed decisions and take responsible actions (United Nations Scientific and Cultural Organization, 1977).

According to UNESCO (2021), “Environmental education is a way of implementing the goals of environmental protection. It is not a separate branch of science but life-long interdisciplinary field of study”. It means education towards the protection and enhancement of the environment.

Environmental Laws

Environmental laws and policies were developed in response to the public perception that human health and the environment were inadequately protected. Environmental law in Nigeria is that branch of Public Law which common rules and regulation to protect the environment. The Mondi Operandi to define Environmental laws depends on an individual environmentalist who is saddled with the responsibility of defining the subject matter. Environmental Law is a complex and interlocking body of treaties, conventions, statures, regulations, and common law that, very broadly, operate to regulate people's interaction on the natural environment (Wilkinson , 2002). Olaniyan et al, (2022), defined environmental law as integrated rules and principles i.e. legal norms, the purpose of which is to achieve environmental conservation. According to Ola (1984),

“Environmental law is seeing as the study of laws concerned with the protection of living thing (human beings inclusive) from the harm that human activity may immediately or eventually cause to them or their species, either directly or to the media and the habits on which they depends. Environmental Law covers the whole universe including not only human beings but also plants, animals, forests, shrubs, refuse, bacterial, diseases and insects”.

It is pertinent to reiterate that before the advent of the 1988. Federal Environment Protection Agency Act No 58 of 1988, there was no concise law to protect the environment or referred to as the National Environmental Law. Environmental law in Nigeria encompasses problem of land use and soil conservation; forestry-wildlife and protected natural area; water management; marine resources and

coastal areas, sanitation and waste management, air quality, hazardous substances, working environment-occupational health and safety, major sources of population/pollutants includes; water pollution, air pollution, auto mobile emission and noise pollution, land degradation and planning, matters of afforestation and deforestation and desertification among others. (Akintayo , 2006)

Theoretical Framework

Ethical Theory on Environmental Sustainability (ETES)

Ethics is a branch of Philosophy that concerns with the study of morality in relation to human conduct in the society, and as its affects human and their fellow and indeed the environment in which they find themselves. Environmental ethics is on justification of the rightness or wrongness of human activities as its affects other non-human members of the society or environment (Eliot, 1993, 286). The Ethicists have propounded different theories to guide people's conduct in order to distinguish the right from the wrong. The main goal of Environmental Ethics theories is on regulation of human behaviours and attitudes towards sustaining the environment. Some Ethical environmental theories that have been propounded by Ethicists are: Platonism. Hedonism, subjectivism, Teleological and Deontologist. The Ethicists are of the belief that environment could be sustained by application of each of these theories. Although, each of the theories has both negative and positive implications on environmental sustainability.

All these Ethical theories on the environmental can be sub-merged as' **Environmental Eclecticism**' which is philosophical-cum environmental attitude that amalgamates the positive aspects of existing ethical theories to form a holistic approach to sustainability and development with respect to non-human aspects and their relationship to the environment.

The environmental eclecticism suggests that no ethical or environmental ethnic is totally defective when applied on environment, and as such it makes efforts to identify the effective aspects of such theories. Environmental eclecticism de-emphasizes the negative aspects of a theory and emphasizes on the need to harness the positive part of each ethical theory and bring them to bear on the environment in order to ensure environmental sustainability and development.

The appropriateness, relevance and justification of the choice of the theory i to the study hinges on the ground that the environment needs to be protected by regulating , guiding and controlling human conduct, behaviours, interaction and attitudes Environmental lducation, aws and policies are meant to regulate and guide human beings behaviours, interaction and attitudes by being able to discern between good and wrong activities on the environment which is the cardinal aim of Environmental education, laws and policies on the environment through creating and racisms people's awareness on environment issues.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The study population comprised, people in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria (Ilaje and Ese-Odo Local Governments areas). The sample size of the study was Four hundred (400) respondents or subjects, selected through a snow-balling sampling technique. Ten communities (10) were selected from each of the two Local Government Areas, respectively from which, forty (40) respondents were selected.

The research instruments used for the study were both quantitative and qualitative. Qualitative data was collected using, a self- structured and developed questionnaire, titled, “Questionnaire on Assessing Public Awareness of s Impact of Environmental Education, Laws and Policies on Environmental Sustainability in Coastal Areas of Ondo State, Nigeria”, fashioned on four – likert rating scale: Strongly agreed (SA), Agreed (A); Disagreed (D); Strong Disagreed (SD) and rated on 4:3:2:1 points, respectively. Qualitative data (primary data) was collected using, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). The research instruments were validated by two experts in Test and Measurement while, it reliability was done through, test- retest method at two weeks interval and 0.71 coefficient reliability was obtained.

Data generated on the demographic characteristics of the respondents were analyzed using, bar charts for age and gender variables, while pie-charts was used to analyze variables likes; marital status and educational qualifications, respectively. Data generated quantitatively was analyzed using, descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency counts and mean), while data got qualitatively were collated, transcribed and analyzed, qualitatively.

Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Results

Analysis of demographic characteristics of the respondents

It is important to describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents, so as to place in proper perspectives their influence on the study. The variables which formed the demographic characteristics were: Age, gender, education and marital status.

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 4.1 above, shows the various age groups which the respondents of the study belong. 25% of the respondents were drawn from the age range of 18 to 25 years. Those within the age range of 26 to 35 years constituted 28% of the respondents. 36 to 45 years also, constituted 28% of the respondents, while the percentage that falls within the age group of 46 and above constituted 19% of the respondents. Therefore, what can be deciphered from the analysis above is that, respondents of different age brackets were involved in the study.

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 4.2 above, x-rays the fact that, females are more prone to poverty and joblessness. This however, informs their dominance on male respondents. Hence, from the analysis above

female constitute 60%, while the 40% are males. This adequately provides information, that the study was not gender biased.

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 4.3 above shows the frequency distribution of the respondents by marital status. Out of 400 respondents, 101 are single, 152 are married, 97 divorced while 50 widowed. Therefore, it can be deduced from the analysis above that, people of different marital status participated in the study. Also, that the study allowed equal access to everybody in the study area without bias on the ground of marital status.

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 4.4 above, shows the educational qualification of the respondents. From the analysis, none respondents have no formal education, 51 primary school leavers, 175 were secondary school leavers, while the remaining 174 were graduates of tertiary institutions. It is evident therefore that people of different educational qualifications and backgrounds were participants of the study in coastal area of Ondo, Nigeria. Further, that people without any educational qualification were not involved in the study.

Research Question One: Are you aware of Environmental education, laws and policies on environmental issues?

Table 1: Showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{x}) on are you aware of Environmental Education, Laws and Policies on environmental issues.

N = 400, C = 2.5								
S/N	Items	SD %	D %	A %	SA %	N	MEAN (\bar{x})	Decision
1	Are you aware that there is Environmental education?	336 84	41 40.25	16 4	7 1.75	400	1.23	Disagreed
2	I do not have awareness and knowledge on environmental education	299 74.75	65 16.25	33 8.25	3 0.75	400	1.35	Disagreed
3	I am aware that there are punishable measures on destructive behaviours on the environment	257 64.25	96 24	34 8.5	13 3.25	400	1.50	Disagreed
4	I am ignorance of legal actions on unfriendly interaction with the environment	8 2	38 9.5	42 10.5	312 78	400	3.64	Agreed
5	Are there existing government policies on the environment	298 74.5	79 19.75	16 4	7 1.75	400	1.33	Disagreed
6	There are no extant government policies on the environment	11 2.75	36 9	94 23.5	259 64.75	400	3.50	Agreed
	TOTAL	1,209 50.37	355 14.79	235 9.79	601 25.01		2.09	Disagreed

Source: Field Study, 2024

N = Total Number of Respondents, C = Cut of points, Mean = \bar{x} , SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed.

Table 1 above, shows the results on research question one. On item (1), responses obtained indicated; 7 (1.75), 16 (4), 41 (10.25) and 336 (84) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (2), the following responses were obtained; 3 (0.75)

33 (8.25), 65 (16.25) and 299 (74.75) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. On item (3), 13 (3.25), 34 (8.5), 96 (24) and 257 (64.25) were got for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed as responses.

On item (4), responses obtained indicated; 312 (78), 42 (10.5), 38 (9.5) and 8 (2) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (5), the following responses were obtained; 7 (1.75), 16 (4), 79 (19.75) and 298 (74.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (6), 259 (64.75), 94 (23.5), 36 (9) and 11 (2.75) responses were got for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

The mean of average rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 2.09$) was lesser than the average of rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 2.5$) therefore, indicated that public did not aware Environmental education, laws and policies on environmental issues in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: Are you aware that environment can be protected through knowledge of Environmental education in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{x}) on are you aware that the environment can be protected through knowledge of Environmental education in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria.

N = 400, C = 2.50								
S/N	Items	SD %	D %	A %	SA %	N	MEAN (\bar{x})	Decision
7	I am aware of environmental education on water protection and other national resources	259 64.75	112 28	14 3.5	15 3.75	400	1.18	Disagreed
8	I am not aware of Environmental Education on protection of the environment	31 7.75	11 2.75	95 23.75	263 65.75	400	3.47	Agreed
9	Are your actions and inactions traceable to your knowledge on Environmental Education?	299 74.75	57 14.25	36 9	8 2	400	1.38	Disagreed
10	Do you believe that your sound Environment Education will inform your positive interaction with the environment?	6 1.5	38 9.5	77 19.25	279 69.75	400	3.57	Agreed
11	Do you think that Environmental Education is for protection of the environment mainly	311 77.75	64 16	19 4.75	6 1.5	400	1.21	Disagreed

12	Is Environmental Education beneficiary to the living organisms?	12 3	28 7	36 9	324 81	400	3.68	Agreed
	TOTAL WEIGHT	918 38.25	310 12.91	277 11.54	895 37.29		2.41	Disagreed

Source: *Field Study, 2024*

N = Total Number of Respondents, C = Cut of points, Mean = \bar{x} , SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed.

Table 2 above, shows the results on research question two. On item (7), responses obtained indicated; 15 (3.75), 14 (3.5), 112 (28) and 259 (64.75) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (8), the following responses were obtained; 263 (65.75), 95 (23.75), 11 (2.75) and 31 (7.75) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. On item (9), 8 (2), 36 (9), 57 (14.25) and 299 (74.75) were got for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed as responses.

On item (10), the following responses were got; 279 (69.75), 77 (19.25), 38 (9.5) and 6 (1.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (11), the following responses were obtained; 6 (1.5), 19 (4.75), 64 (16) and 311 (77.75) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Finally, on item (12), the following responses were obtained; 324 (81), 36 (9), 28 (7) and 12 (3) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Generally speaking, the average rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 2.5$) is higher than the mean of average of rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 2.41$). This indicate that public was not aware of strategic impact of Environmental education on protection of the environment in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research Question Three: Do you think that Environmental Laws can adequately halt all forms of people’s destructive and hazardous behaviours on environment in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{x}) on do you think that Environmental Laws can adequately halt all forms of people’s destructive and hazardous behaviours on environment in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria.

N = 400, C = 2.5								
S/N	Items	SD %	D %	A %	SA %	N	MEAN (\bar{x})	Decision
13	Are you aware of environmental laws on natural resources conservation?	299 74.75%	62 15.5	20 5	19 4.75	400	1.55	Disagreed
14	Do you think that environmental law on the protection of the environment are not effective?	3 0.75	14 3.5	89 22.25	294 73.5	400	3.68	Agreed
15	Are environmental laws enough to protest the environment?	274 68.5	96 24	16 4	14 3.5	400	1.42	Disagreed
16	Are you restraining your destructive behaviors do to environment laws?	247 61.75	99 16.5	33 8.25	21 5.25	400	1.57	Disagreed
17	Do environmental law conscious have position impact on your interaction with the environmental resource?	301 75.25	66 16.5	29 7.25	4 3.5	400	1.34	Disagreed
18	Are the existing environmental laws restricting your hazardous behaviors on the environment	296 74	66 16.5	31 7.75	7 1.75	400	1.37	Disagreed
	TOTAL WEIGHT	1420 59.16	403 16.79	218 9.08	359 14.95		1.82	Disagreed

Source: *Field Survey, 2024*

N = Total Number of Respondents, C = Cut of points, Mean = \bar{x} , SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed.

Table 3 above, shows the responses on research question three. On item (13), responses obtained indicated; 19 (4.75), 20 (5), 02 (15.5) and 299 (74.75) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (14), the following responses were obtained; 294 (73.5), 89 (22.25), 14 (3.5) and 3 (0.75) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. On item (15), 14 (3.5), 16 (4), 96 (24) and 274 (68.5) were got for

strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed as responses. On item (16), the following responses were obtained; 21 (5.25), 33 (8.25), 99 (16.25) and 38 (9.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

On item (17), the following responses were obtained; 4 (3.5), 29 (7.25), 66 (16.5) and 301 (75.25) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (18), the following responses were got; 7 (1.75), 31 (7.75), 66 (16.5) and 296 (74) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Generally, the result revealed that the average rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 2.5$) is higher than the mean of average of rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 1.82$). Thus, indicated that public was not aware that Environmental laws could halt all forms of human beings destructive and hazardous behaviours on environment in the coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

The results on research question one indicated that public was not aware of Environmental education, laws and policies on environmental issues in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria. The result is in consonance with the view of Olajire (2020), that lack of education on environmental results into human beings' destructive actions. Green gas emission, improper waste dumping on rivers, oceans, oil drilling, fossil fuels, bush burning tc are environmental challenges caused by lack of human awareness on the need to protect the environment. Moreover, air pollution, deforestation, destruction of aqua-habitat are caused by lack of awareness on Environmental education, laws and policies. Anderson (2019), however opined on the need to have a safe and quality environment through understanding of environmental problems and the need to protect the problems and the ecosystem by raising people's awareness on the environment and that it could be achieved through Environmental education. The above submissions were further corroborated by the were obtained from the discussants during the FGD sessions. A respondents had this to say;

“I am not aware that there are Environmental education, laws and policies to protect our interactions on water resources in this community”

A male respondent at Oke -Ayetoro Community during FGDs

The results on research question two revealed that public was not aware that having knowledge of Environmental education could influence their positive behavior and attitudes towards environmental resources. The findings aligns with the submission of Erinsakin (2022)

that environmental degradation and mismanagement are partly human activities caused by lack of environmental protection, skills, knowledge and information. Hence, suggested that Environmental Education is a positive strategic approach to conserve, water resources, ecosystem, biosphere and other elements of the environment. The finding is in consonance with the view of a respondent or discussant during the FGD sessions.

“My interaction with the environment at all times are mainly for survival. I am doing everything possible to get anything that I need from water. I don’t have a knowledge of Environmental Education that will restrict me from doing so.

A female discuss out at Safa- Arogo community durin - FGDS.

The result on research question three indicated that public do not aware that Environmental Laws could put an end to all forms of human destructive and hazardous behaviours towards the environment.

A discussant said during- FGDS

“There are no laws that will not allow me to get what I need from the environment and on the way I want it”.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, conclusion were made that public was not aware of Environmental education, laws and policies on environment protection, conservation and management and its impact to stop. Also, through Environmental education, laws and policies people’s destructive and hazardous behaviours on the environment could be controlled in coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were made;

1. More pro-active strategies to achieve environmental education goals should be adopted to ensure that public is well educated and sensitized on the environment, and allied issues.
2. Both print and electronic media should be made use to create public awareness on Environmental laws and policies in the coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria.
3. People whose their actions and inactions are dangerous to the environment should be made to face the wrath of Environmental laws. This will create public attention on the existing laws and policies.
4. Efforts should be made by government to ensure that Environmental Laws and policies are well implemented in the coastal areas of Ondo State, Nigeria.

- Public should be educated by the stakeholders on environmental protection or environmentalists on the need to protect the natural resources.

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